

Report of the VERT AeroSolfd project – a Horizon Europe Framework Programme

VERT AeroSolfd: Tailpipe retrofit solutions for gasoline vehicles

Report on vehicle exhaust analysis PCDD/Fs, PAHs, NPAHs (WP1, Task 1.3)

(VERT Secondary emissions test)

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Time Frame of Project

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Executive summary

Gasoline-direct injection vehicles (GDI) are now operated on European roads in the millions with yet unknown impact on human health and the environment. GDI technology is on the rise in other markets too such as Japan, U.S.A. and in middle and far eastern countries.

Mitsubishi started the mass production of GDI vehicles (Mitsubishi Carisma, 1.8 L, Euro-3) already in 1997. In the Swiss GASOMEF project (2013-2017) we tested this vehicle together with six Euro-4, -5, and Euro-6 GDI vehicles and compared their emissions with an Euro-5 diesel vehicle (Peugeot 4008, 1.6 L) equipped with a state-of-the-art diesel particle filter (DPF). As an outcome of this project we found that particle number (PN) emissions of the GDI-technology, on average, was higher than 2.0×10^{12} particles/km clearly exceeding the current PN limit of 6×10^{11} particles/km. In comparison to the bench mark diesel vehicle with DPF, PN emissions of these GDI vehicles were 2 to 3 orders of magnitude higher than those of the diesel vehicle. This indicates the potential that the particle filter technology has on PN emissions of GDI-vehicles and was motivation for the AeroSolfd project to develop and apply retrofit solutions for pre-Euro-7 gasoline vehicles.

Another outcome of the GASOMEF project was that the emissions of genotoxic PAHs of GDI vehicles were unexpectedly high as well. The mean genotoxic potential of GDI-exhausts exceeded the one of the benchmark diesel vehicle by a factor of 17. In comparison to the EU ambient air limit for benzo(a)pyrene of 1 ng/m^3 , the mean genotoxic potential of GDI exhausts was 750 ng/m^3 . Thus on average GDI exhaust concentrations of carcinogenic PAHs are 750-times above the ambient air limit. We concluded that GDI-vehicles are an important source for combustion-generated nanoparticles with diameters of around 60-80 nm, even smaller than those of e.g. Corona viruses. GDI-particles also carry genotoxic PAHs and if inhaled will deliver this critical compounds to the alveolar regions of the human lungs acting like Trojan Horses.

In the AeroSolfd project it was our motivation to implement state-of-the art particle filters in two widely used Euro-6b gasoline vehicles and test their performance under transient and steady-state driving. The GDI vehicle selected was a VW Golf TSI (Euro-6b, model year 2016, 1.4 L, 92 kW). In addition, we also tested and retrofitted a Fiat 500X (Euro-6b, model year 2016, 1.6 L, 91 kW) with multi-point injection (MPI) technology. For each vehicle, retrofitted particle filters of the type of multi-cell wall-flow Cordierite filters were integrated in the tailpipe systems. Thus, both vehicles could be studied on the chassis dynamometer of the BFH in Biel in standard configurations without filter and with retrofitted filters.

The worldwide harmonized light vehicle test cycle (WLTC), was applied started in cold- and hot conditions and a steady state cycle (SSC) representing constant driving at urban-, extra-urban, highway and motorway conditions and an idle phase. A comprehensive characterization of gaseous, liquid and solid exhaust constituents was performed. The focus was on toxic, carcinogenic and mutagenic compounds such as polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), nitrated PAHs (nitro-PAHs), polychlorinated dibenzodioxins (PCDDs) and polychlorinated dibenzofurans (PCDFs).

The characterization of the particles is not part of this report in which we focus on the analysis of toxic semi-volatile compounds, typically present in micro-, nano- and pico-gram concentrations. Dependent on the exhaust gas flow and temperature these compounds can be found adsorbed on particles, dissolved in the water phase or in the gas-phase. All-glass sampling devices were used to collect dilute vehicle exhausts from the constant volume sampling (CVS) system.

After sampling the glass devices were rinsed and combined extracts were purified further with normal-phase liquid chromatography (LC). Fractions of these extracts were injected to a gas chromatography system (GC) coupled to a high-resolution mass spectrometer (Orbitrap-MS).

In other words, the protocols of the VERT secondary emissions test (VSET) were applied here to test emissions toxic compounds in the best case scenario, without additional uptake of chlorine from gasoline containing scavengers such as 1,2-dichloro-ethane.

Particle number emissions of vehicle V1 (Fiat 500X) were 1.0×10^{11} and 0.4×10^{11} particles/km in the cWLTC and hWLTC, respectively. Considerably lower PN emissions of $0.03 - 1.0 \times 10^{10}$ particles/km were observed in the SSC. PN emissions of vehicle V2 (Golf TSI) were 5 to 10-fold higher, at 6.1×10^{11} and 6.2×10^{11} particles/km in the cWLTC and hWLTC. PN emissions of the GDI vehicle in the SSC were higher too compared to V1, which uses the MPI technology.

The higher PN emissions of V2 compared to V1 also affected PN filtration efficiencies to some degree, which reached 95.8% and 95.1% for filter F1 on vehicle V1 and 98.3% and 98.4% for filter F2 on vehicle V2. We conclude that both retrofitted filter are highly efficient with respect to nanoparticles, indicating that soot particles are retained and possibly converted in these filters. This brings us to the question how emissions of semi-volatile compounds like PAHs, nitrated PAHs and PCDD/Fs are affected by these filters.

Genotoxic PAH emissions of vehicle V1 (Fiat 500X, Euro-6b), equipped with the MPI technology, were 30%-40% lower than those of vehicle V2 (VW Golf FSI, Euro-6b), which was a GDI vehicle. This follows the PN trends, which were 5x and 15x lower for the MPI than the GDI vehicle in the cold and hot WLTC.

In the GASOMEF project, three of the four proto-type filters tested did lower genotoxic PAH emissions by 45%-83%, while one filter showed no net PAH reduction.

In the AeroSolfd project, one of the two filters tested did lower genotoxic PAH emissions of the GDI vehicle (VW Golf) by 40% and 70%, while filter F1 on the MPI vehicle (Fiat 500X) could not convert genotoxic PAHs and in one case released stored material again.

No significant formation of nitro-PAHs could be detected in both filters. This could be an indication that nitrating species are not abundant in gasoline exhausts compared to diesel exhausts. Furthermore, higher temperatures and shorter residence times, which are reached in GPFs do not favor a nitration of PAHs, which can occur even in cold ambient conditions.

The *de novo* formation potential for PCDDs and PCDFs is considered as low for both filters. No indications for an efficient PCDD/F formation could be found under the given experimental conditions. Nevertheless, it has to be mentioned that the filters were not tested in the worst case scenario, with a forced intake of chlorine via e.g. the co-combustion of scavengers like 1,2-dichloro-ethane.

We conclude that GPFs have a large potential to reduce nanoparticle emissions and to lower genotoxic PAHs. High PN efficiencies of >98% were obtained with the newly designed particle filter on the GDI-vehicle (VW Golf) and genotoxic PAH emissions were lowered by 40%-70% as well.

Filtration efficiencies on the MPI-vehicle (Fiat 500X) of >95% are still high, but no net conversion of genotoxic PAHs could be observed in this case.

In summary, a big step towards best-available filter technologies for gasoline vehicles has been made in the AeroSolfd project that allows an efficient removal of soot nanoparticles. It is not clear yet, if a combustion of accumulated soot and adsorbed PAHs can be achieved with optimized catalytic coatings. Indications that these critical compounds do accumulate in filters and can be released again under high load operations have been observed for one of the two filters tested in the AeroSolfd project and in one of the four proto-type filters tested in the GASOMEF project.

The retrofitting of GPFs to Euro-5 and Euro-6b gasoline vehicles has been demonstrated with positive effects on particle number emissions and to some extent on genotoxic PAHs. Due to substantial health risks associated with the inhalation of non-filtered gasoline and diesel exhausts, which include numerous nanoparticles and relevant amounts of genotoxic PAHs, filters should be implemented in all next-generation vehicles (Euro-7) and retrofitted in high polluters such as Euro-4, Euro-5 and Euro-6 GDI-vehicles, best on a global scale.

Nanoparticles act as Trojan horses, transporting adsorbed semi-volatile compounds such as the genotoxic PAHs, nitro-PAHs and PCDD/Fs deep into the human lung. They even can penetrate the alveolar membrane reaching the blood circulation. This is a serious health threat and well documented for U.S. miners that were exposed to non-filtered diesel exhausts.

We report that gasoline vehicle exhausts can also contain numerous soot-like nanoparticles carrying genotoxic PAHs. In this respect they have a similar chemical composition like the one of non-treated diesel exhaust. Non-treated diesel exhaust is considered as class 1 carcinogen by the WHO, inducing lung cancer and many other kinds of cancer in humans. We expect that the WHO will also classify non-filtered exhausts of gasoline vehicles soon in a fast growing vehicle market.

List of abbreviations

catGPF	Catalytically active Gasoline Particle Filter
CVS	Constant Volume Sampling system
cWLTC	Cold-started WLTC
DPF	Diesel Particle Filter
EPA	Environmental Protection Agency
FID	Flame Ionization Detector
GC-HRMS	Gas Chromatography High-Resolution Mass Spectrometry
GDI	Gasoline Direct Injection
GPF	Gasoline Particle Filter
hWLTC	Hot-started WLTC
IARC	International Agency for Research on Cancer
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
MPI	Multi Point Injection
NPAHs	Nitrated Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons
Nitro-PAHs	Nitrated Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons,
PAH	Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons
PCDDs	Polychlorinated dibenzodioxins
PCDD/Fs	Polychlorinated dibenzodioxins/furans
PCDFs	Polychlorinated dibenzofurans
PN	Particle Number
SSC	Steady State Cycle
SP	Sampling Point
TEF	Toxicity Equivalent Factor
TEQ	Toxicity Equivalent
VSET	VERT secondary emissions test
WLTC	World Harmonized Light Vehicle Test Cycle
WHO	World Health Organization

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Scope of the AeroSolfd project

Numbers of gasoline direct injection (GDI) vehicles and multi-point injection (MPI) vehicles are on the rise in fleets worldwide. Many of these vehicles are on European roads without filter technology despite their high particle number emissions. We have shown in the Swiss GASOMEF project that a fleet of eight GDI vehicles release, on average, 2.5×10^{12} particles/km in the cold-started WLTC and 2.0×10^{12} particles/km in the hot-started WLTC (Munoz et al., 2018a). This compares with PN emissions of a benchmark diesel vehicle (Peugeot, Euro-5) with integrated diesel particle filter (DPF) of 4.0×10^{10} and 2.8×10^9 particles/km in the cold- and hot-started WLTC. In other words, PN emissions of the tested GDI vehicles exceeded those of a diesel vehicle with particle filter 60- to 700-fold.

We showed on four prototype GPFs that a filtration of particles from GDI-vehicles is possible (Munoz et al., 2018b). Filtration efficiencies of these prototype filters varied from 60% to >98%. However, often they were lower than 98%, which is the limit to reach for VERT-certified filters.

Effects on PAH emissions including the genotoxic ones were in general lower than PN effects and varied considerably from filter to filter. Efficiencies also varied from PAH to PAH and their volatility and reactivity are important properties that affect the store-and-release behavior and the conversion efficiencies of PAHs.

In the AeroSolfd project, two new Cordierite-based wall-flow filters have been developed for gasoline vehicles by one of our industrial partner with improved porosity and filtration efficiencies. It is our goal to study effects of these two filters suitable for retrofitting on solid, liquid and gaseous exhaust constituents and to assess their potential for secondary emissions, which may form in filters (VERT secondary emissions test, VSET).

From previous work we know that additional PAHs can form from soot combustion, that nitration of PAHs can occur in filters (Heeb et al., 2008, 2010) and in some special cases catalysts used for soot oxidation can also support a de novo formation of PCDDs and PCDFs (Heeb et al., 2005, 2007, 2013). Even bio-diesel, which typically contains some ppm potassium can turn an iron-catalyzed DPF into an efficient source of PCDD/Fs (Heeb et al., 2015).

In other words, catalysts used for efficient soot generation in filters also affect the chemistry in filters with respect to the composition of semi-volatile adsorbates and with it the overall exhaust toxicity.

1. Vehicle characteristics, test cycles and testing

Both vehicles were tested at the chassis dynamometer of the UASB in Nidau. A scheme of the dynamometer and the sampling points are given in **Figure 1**. Two gasoline vehicles one with GDI – and one with MPI-technology were tested without and with integrated particle filters.

Figure 1: Scheme of the chassis dynamometer at UASB in Nidau. Different sampling points are indicated.

Table 1 reports some characteristics of the tested vehicles. A batch of commercial gasoline E10 with an ethanol content up to 10% was used as fuel in the project. Both vehicles were in compliance with the Euro-6b legislation with limit values for CO, THC, NO_x and PN of 1000, 100, 60 mg/km and 6.0 x 10¹² particles/km based on the European drive cycle.

Table 1: Characteristics of the test vehicles.

Vehicle	Fiat 500X	VW Golf 1.4 TSI
Model year	2016	2016
Gearbox	M5	M6
Mileage (km)	49396	71789
First registration	27.10.2016	05.04.2016
Engine type	55263842	CZCA
Number of cylinder	4 (in line)	4 (in line)
Displacement (ccm)	1598	1395
Nominal power (kW)	91 (5500 rpm)	92 (5000 rpm)
Maximum torque (Nm)	152 (4500 rpm)	200 (1400 rpm)
Injection type	MPI	DI
Curb weight (kg)	1350	1247
Gross vehicle weight (kg)	1875	1770
Maximum speed	180	204
Exhaust aftertreatment system	TWC	TWC
Fulfilled emission standard	Euro 6b	Euro 6b

In other words, the PN limit for these Euro-6b vehicles was 10 times higher than the one for Euro-5 and Euro-6 diesel vehicles, which are limited to 6.0×10^{11} particles/km. From September 2017 on, the PN limit for new GDI vehicles was lowered to 6.0×10^{11} particles/km as well.

We decided to rely on the world harmonized light vehicle test cycle (WLTC) shown in **Figure 2**, which does represent real world driving and is the legally binding test cycle for post-Euro-6b vehicles. The WLTC includes many transients and realistic acceleration and deceleration events and extended high-speed operation (**Fig. 2**). The WLTC includes urban (26 km/h), extra-urban (45 km/h), highway (61 km/h) and motorway (94 km/h) driving with a total cycle time of 30 min. The WLTC was investigated under cold start- (cWLTC) and hot engine/catalyst-conditions (hWLTC) throughout the project.

Figure 2: The cold- and hot-started WLTC was used as the transient test cycle throughout the project.

In addition, a steady state cycle (SSC) covering constant vehicle operation at 26, 45, 61, 94 km/h and at idling was also included to investigate in detail the characteristics and chemical composition of the released nanoparticles (**Fig. 3**). The SSC covers the mean velocity regimes of the four WLTC phases and includes an equally long hot-idle phase. The cycle was driven from high loads (94 km/h) to idle. Each stage was kept for 20 minutes to yield a total cycle time of 100 min.

Figure 3: A steady state cycle (SSC), representing the mean velocities of the four WLTC phases and an idling phase, was used to study exhaust compositions and particle properties under stable conditions.

2. Characteristics of gasoline particle filters (GPFs) and tests performed

Ceramic multi-cell wall-flow filters based on Cordierite are widely used for diesel engines. Such filters can reach high filtration efficiencies in a few minutes after a soot cake has formed. But gasoline engines produce smaller particles and the tendency to build-up a soot cake is less pronounced. As a consequence, filtration efficiencies above 98%, which are required for VERT certification, are difficult to reach with GPFs (Munoz et al., 2018b).

One of our industrial partners has contributed with two new Cordierite-based GPFs with adopted porosity. Two variants with filter volumes of 1.64 L (132 mm x 120 mm) and 1.16 L (103 mm x 139 mm) were tested.

A three-week sampling campaign was organized at the chassis dynamometer of the University of Applied Sciences Berne in Nidau in November 2023. In the AeroSolfd project, two vehicles were tested in more detail following the procedures of the VERT secondary emissions test.

Vehicle V1 (Fiat 500X, 1.6L, model year 2016, Euro-6b) had a multi-point injection (MPI) system while vehicle V2 (VW TSI, 1.4 L, model year 2016, Euro-6d) had a direct injection (DI) system. Both vehicles were fueled with E10 gasoline and could be retrofitted with well-integrated filters F1 and F2. The vehicles were tested in the cold- and hot-started transient WLTC (T1C, T1H) and the hot-started steady-state cycle (S1H). In addition, both vehicles were tested again in the same cycles and conditions without filters, which were removed for these tests.

Table 2 lists all performed tests and the abbreviations used. In addition, two blank samples of dilution air of the CVS tunnel were collected.

Table 2: Sampling of semi-volatile compounds (PAHs, NPAHs, PCDD/Fs)

Date	Abbrev.	Configuration
Monday, 13. November 2023		Installation
Tuesday, 14. November 2023	BL-420	Blank sample, dilution air CVS tunnel (60 Min)
Tuesday, 14. November 2023	BL-421	Blank sample, dilution air CVS tunnel (60 Min)
Wednesday, 15. November 2023	V1F1T1C-422	V1, F1, 1 x cold WLTC (30 Min)
Wednesday, 15. November 2023	V1F1T1H-423	V1, F1, 1 x hot WLTC (30 Min)
Thursday, 16. November 2023	V1F1S1H-424	V1, F1, 1 x hot SSC (100 Min)
Friday, 17. November 2023		Removal of particle filter F1
Monday, 20. November 2023	V1T1C-425	V1, 1 x cold WLTC (30 Min)
Monday, 20. November 2023	V1T1H-426	V1, 1 x hot WLTC (30 Min)
Tuesday, 21. November 2023	V1S1H-427	V1, 1 x hot SSC (100 Min)
Tuesday, 21. November 2023		Installation of vehicle V2 with filter F2
Thursday, 23. November 2023	V2F2T1C-431	V2, F2, 1 x cold WLTC (30 Min) *
Wednesday, 22. November 2023	V2F2T1C-429	V2, F2, 1 x hot WLTC (30 Min)
Thursday, 23. November 2023	V2F2S1H-430	V2, F2, 1 x hot SSC (100 Min)
Friday, 24. November 2023		Removal of particle filter F2
Monday, 27. November 2023	V2T1C-432	V2, 1 x cold WLTC (30 Min)
Monday, 27. November 2023	V2T1H-433	V2, 1 x hot WLTC (30 Min)
Tuesday, 28. November 2023	V2S1H-434	V2, 1 x hot SSC (100 Min)
Tuesday, 28. November 2023		Deinstallation

* Due to cold start problems with vehicle V2 the test V2F2T1C-428 had to be repeated.

3. VERT Secondary Emissions Test (VSET)

The VERT secondary emissions test (VSET) was originally developed for testing the performance of particle filters for heavy-duty diesel engines (Heeb et al., 2005). In later years, the test was adopted to sample exhausts of vehicles operated in transient cycles such as the WLTC together with steady-state cycles. Emissions of vehicles under transient conditions can be orders of magnitude higher than under steady-state conditions. This has been observed before when testing a fleet of seven GDI vehicles of the Euro-2 to Euro-6 technology (Munoz et al, 2018a). In other words, it is meaningful to test on-road vehicles in transient operation rather than under steady-state conditions. Especially the fast variations of exhaust flow rates can have an impact on filtration efficiencies in downstream filters.

Below we describe emissions of semi-volatile compounds such as PAHs, NPAHs, PCDDs and PCDFs. The volatility of these compounds varies considerably with 2-ring PAHs being the most volatile and 6-ring PAHs, nitrated PAHs and highly chlorinated dibenzodioxins and furans being the least volatile compounds. The chemical reactivity under the temperatures in the engine, converter and filter vary as well, affecting the emissions. Thus a highly volatile compound will quickly penetrate a filter, while highly reactive and non-volatile compounds will be converted in filters to new compounds.

4. Emissions of genotoxic compounds

4.1. Emissions of genotoxic polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs)

Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) are a large class of compounds. **Figure 4** displays the 16 priority PAHs analyzed. Some of these PAHs contribute to the overall genotoxicity of exhausts and ambient air in traffic-affected areas. Thus, emission levels for these critical compounds are important to be able to assess the genotoxic risks of current GDI- and MPI-vehicles and of new filter technology.

Figure 4: Chemical structures of the investigated PAHs. Compounds labeled with asterisks are carcinogenic to humans according to the WHO. The 16 priority PAHs are naphthalene (1*), acenaphthylene (2), acenaphthene (3), fluorene (4), phenanthrene (5), anthracene (6), fluoranthene (7), pyrene (8), benzo(a)anthracene (9*), chrysene (10*), benzo(b)fluoranthene (11*), benzo(k)fluoranthene (12*), benzo(a)pyrene (13*), dibenzo(a,h)anthracene (14*), benzo(g,h,i)perylene (15) and indeno(1,2,3-cd)pyrene (16*). Respective toxicity-equivalence factors (TEFs) in relation to benzo(a)pyrene (13*, 1.0x) are indicated in brackets.

These 16 priority PAHs include one 2-ring-, five 3-ring, four 4-ring, four 5-ring and two 6-ring PAHs. The volatility of these PAHs decreases with increasing ring numbers. In other words volatile 2-ring and 3-ring PAHs may penetrate a particle filter while 6-ring PAHs may accumulate in a filter, depending on exhaust flow rates and temperatures.

PAHs which are carcinogenic to humans according to the WHO are labeled with asterisks (**Figure 4**).

Dilute exhausts have been sampled from the CVS tunnel for all vehicle configurations throughout the campaign (**Table 2**). For this purpose, aliquots of diluted exhausts were collected in all-glass sampling devices. Overall 12 sampling devices have been exposed to vehicle exhausts collecting solid, condensed (liquid) and gaseous exhaust constituents. In addition, two samples of dilution air were taken from the CVS tunnel, which represent background air concentration at the BFH in Biel/Nidau.

After a multi-step clean-up procedure, these samples were analyzed for PAHs and related compounds with GC-HRMS. Respective clean-up and analysis procedures have been reported elsewhere (Heeb et al., 2007, 2008, Munoz et al., 2018a,b).

Figure 5 displays concentrations (ng/m^3) of groups of PAHs in diluted exhaust gas from the CVS. Compared are sum concentrations of all 16 priority PAHs, of carcinogenic PAHs in accordance to the U.S. EPA and the IARC-WHO. The EPA list excludes chrysene (**10**) and includes benzo(a)anthracene (**9**), benzo(b)fluoranthene (**11**), benzo(k)fluoranthene (**12**), benzo(a)pyrene (**13**), dibenzo(a,h)anthracene (**14**) and indeno(1,2,3-cd)pyrene (**16**) like the IARC list.

Displayed are sum concentrations in exhausts of the cold- (blue) and hot-started (red) WLTC and the steady state cycle (black) together with concentrations in dilution air (gray, $n=2$) sampled through the CVS tunnel. Compared are data of vehicles V1 (Fiat 500X, MPI, Euro-6b) and V2 (VW Golf TSI, GDI, Euro-6b) without and with filter F1 and F2.

Figure 5: Concentrations (ng/m^3) of PAHs in diluted vehicle exhausts from cold- (blue) and hot-started (red) WLTCs and the steady state cycle (black). Levels in CVS dilution air (gray) are given as well. Vehicles V1 (Fiat 500X) and V2 (VW Golf TSI) without and with particle filters F1 and F2 are compared. Sums of the 16 priority PAHs (left), of carcinogenic PAHs according to the EPA and the IARC and the weighted genotoxic potential (right) are displayed.

PAH concentrations in dilute exhausts of the steady state cycle (black) are always lower than those in the transient WLTC. In most cases, PAH concentrations in CVS dilution air are comparably high as those from diluted exhausts of the SSC.

Genotoxic PAH emissions at transient driving are considerably higher than those at steady-state driving (**Figure 5**). In most cases PAH emissions under cold-start (blue) conditions are slightly higher than under hot-start (red) conditions.

Overall, PAH emissions in the cold- and hot-WLTC of vehicles V1 and V2 are similar. But effects of filters F1 and F2 differ to some degree. Filter F1 did not induce a significant reduction of genotoxic PAH emissions, while filter F2 lowered genotoxic PAH emissions, both in the cold- and hot-WLTC (**Figure 5**, right diagrams). This effect is not observed when comparing the sums of 16 priority PAHs (**Figure 5**, left).

Figure 6: Concentrations (ng/m^3) of 16 priority PAHs in dilute vehicle exhausts from cold- (blue) and hot-started (red) WLTCs and the steady state cycle (black). Levels in CVS dilution air (gray) are given as well. Vehicles V1 (Fiat 500X) and V2 (VW Golf TSI), without and with particle filters F1 and F2 are compared. Genotoxic PAHs are labeled with asterisks.

As shown in **Figure 6**, concentrations of the 16 priority PAHs vary by three orders of magnitude. In general, PAH concentrations in the transient WLTC (blue, red) exceed those in the SSC (black). Respective PAH levels in diluted exhausts of the SSC are close to the levels found in CVS dilution air. Thus transient driving results in considerably higher PAH emissions than steady-state driving. This has also been observed for particle number emissions, which are two to three orders of magnitude higher under transient driving than under steady-state conditions.

Most abundant is the 2-ring PAH Naphthalene (**1**) with concentrations in diluted exhausts of 400-1800 ng/m³ (**Figure 6**). The most abundant 3-ring and 4-ring PAHs are phenanthrene (**5**) and chrysene (**10**) with concentrations of 400-1300 and 5-25 ng/m³, respectively. The most abundant 5-ring and 6-ring PAHs are benzo(b)fluoranthene (**11**) and indeno-1,2,3-c,d-pyrene (**15**) with concentrations of 1-5 and 0.3-2 ng/m³. In most cases, PAH emissions in the cold-WLTC (blue) exceeded those of the hot-WLTC (red).

Figure 7 displays conversion efficiencies (CE) of filter F1 on vehicle V1 (top) and filter F2 on vehicle V2 (bottom) in the cold- (blue) and hot- (red) WLTC. Conversion efficiencies were calculated according the formula $CE = ((\text{conc. with filter} / \text{conc. without filter}) - 1)$. In other words, if concentrations after a filter exceed those without filter positive CEs are obtained, if PAHs are converted in the filter, negative CEs are observed.

Effects of filter F1 on PAH emissions often lead to positive values. Efficiencies of PAH sum values (**Figure 7**, right) vary in a smaller range from 0.0 to 0.35 in the cold and from -0.21 to 0.07 in the hot WLTC, respectively.

This contrasts findings for filter F2, tested on vehicle V2 (**Figure 7**, bottom), which showed systematic trends. In general, CE data from cold- and hot-WLTC are comparable for filter F2. Effects of F2 on 2-ring- and 3-ring PAHs resulted in positive CE values. Those of 5-ring and 6-ring-PAHs, which include the most genotoxic PAHs, are negative indicating a net adsorption and conversion in filter F2.

Among the 4-ring PAHs, filter efficiencies on fluoranthene (**7**) and pyrene (**8**) resulted in positive values of 0.23-0.43 and 0.36-0.45, respectively. Those of benzo(a)anthracene (**10**) and chrysene (**9**) were negative with -0.15 to -0.23 and -0.39 to -0.48. In other words, benzo(a)anthracene and chrysene are converted in filter F2 to some degree, but fluoranthene and pyrene were not and could escape from the filter.

As mentioned before, the volatility of a PAH can also affect the conversion efficiency of a filter. Volatile PAHs such as 2-ring- and 3-ring PAHs can penetrate filters depending on the exhaust temperatures. The less volatile 5-ring and 6-ring PAHs can be stored in filters and eventually converted to some degree or released again at higher loads and higher exhaust temperatures. This is demonstrated in filter F2, which showed systematic trends among the 16 PAHs which correlate with the volatility of a PAH (**Figure 7**, bottom).

Figure 7: Conversion efficiencies of the 16 priority PAHs in filters F1 (top) and filter F2 (bottom) from cold- (blue) and hot-started (red) WLTCs. Conversion efficiencies (CEs) are calculated according to the formula $CE = ((\text{conc. with filter} / \text{conc. without filter}) - 1)$. Negative CEs indicate a reduction of PAHs, positive CEs indicate higher emissions after the filter. Next to the 16 priority PAHs also CEs of their sum, the sums of carcinogenic PAHs and the genotoxic potential are displayed (right bars).

4.2. Emissions of nitrated polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (Nitro-PAHs)

Nitration of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons results in the formation of nitrated PAHs. Nitration reactions often are regio-selective and can lead to mono-, di- and even tri-nitro-PAHs. Nitration reactions have been observed in ambient air on particle surfaces and in droplets (aqueous solutions). But nitro-PAHs also form during combustion in diesel and gasoline engines and are found down-stream of catalytic converters such a particle filters (Heeb et al., 2008, 2010). **Figure 8** displays chemical structures of detected nitro-PAHs.

Figure 8: Chemical structures of 1-nitro-naphthalene (**17**), 2-nitro-naphthalene (**18**), 9-nitro-anthracene (**19**), 3-nitro-phenanthrene (**20**), 9-nitro-phenanthrene (**21**), 3-nitro-fluoranthene (**22**), 1-nitro-pyrene (**23**) and 2-nitro-pyrene (**24**). For comparison, the structure of pyrene (**8**) is given as well.

The volatility of a nitro-PAH is lower than the one of the corresponding parent PAH. In other words, if semi-volatile PAHs can accumulate in particle filters, the corresponding nitro-PAHs should be stored in filters too. Furthermore, a nitration of adsorbed PAHs, which are exposed to NO, NO₂ and other nitrating species for extended times, can occur in particle filters. To assess the risks of a secondary formation of nitro-PAHs in particle filter is an important aspect of the VSET.

Figure 9 displays concentrations (ng/m^3) of the sum of all detected nitro-PAHs and of sums of 2-ring-, 3-ring- and 4-ring-nitro-PAHs in dilute exhausts of vehicles V1 and V2 without and with filters F1 and F2. Nitro-PAH emissions in transient cycles exceeded those from steady-state driving in most cases as observed before for PAHs. Emissions under cold- (blue) and hot-start (red) conditions are comparably high and range from 2.2-5.2, 0.3-1.5 and 0-1.2 ng/m^3 for 2-ring-, 3-ring- and 4-ring nitro-PAHs, respectively.

Nitro-PAH emissions with filters are as high as those without filters. No systematic filter effects could be observed for these nitro-PAHs.

Figure 9: Concentrations (ng/m^3) of nitro-PAHs in dilute vehicle exhausts from the cold- (blue) and hot-started (red) WLTC and the steady state cycle (black). Levels in CVS dilution air (gray) are given as well. Vehicles V1 and V2 without and with particle filters F1 and F2 are compared. Sums of all nitro-PAHs (left), and sums of 2-ring-, 3-ring-, and 4-ring-nitro-PAHs are displayed.

Figure 10 displays concentrations (ng/m^3) of individual nitro-PAHs detected in dilute exhausts of vehicles V1 and V2 without and with filters. Most abundant is 1-nitro-naphthalene (**17**) with concentrations of 0.8 – 4.2 ng/m^3 . Emissions of 2-nitro-naphthalene (**18**) are 3-5 times lower in all cases. Of the 3-ring- and 4-ring-nitro-PAHs, 9-nitro-anthracene (**19**) and 1-nitro-pyrene (**23**) are most abundant. Concentrations of 9-nitro-anthracene varied from 0.1 to 1.2 ng/m^3 , those of 1-nitro-pyrene from 0 to 1.0 ng/m^3 .

In other words, nitro-PAH concentrations are 2 to 3 orders of magnitude lower than those of respective parent PAHs. For comparison, exhaust concentrations of pyrene (**8**), the precursor of 1-nitro-pyrene (**23**), are displayed as well in **Figure 10**. Pyrene concentrations varied from 40 to 170 ng/m^3 . Thus, less than 1% of the pyrene found in dilute exhaust is converted to 1-nitro-pyrene.

Figure 10: Concentrations (ng/m^3) of individual nitro-PAHs in dilute vehicle exhausts from the cold- (blue) and hot-started (red) WLTC and the steady state cycle (black). Levels in CVS dilution air (gray) are given as well. Vehicles V1 and V2 without and with particle filters F1 and F2 are presented. For comparison, emissions of pyrene are displayed as well.

We have shown that certain nitro-PAHs can form de novo in diesel particle filters (Heeb et al., 2010). It was found that 1-nitro-naphthalene (**17**) can be formed in DPFs with low and high oxidation potential, while 2-nitro-naphthalene (**18**) is converted under the same conditions. Accordingly, we showed that 9-nitro-phenanthrene (**21**) is formed in certain DPFs, but 3-nitro-phenanthrene (**20**) is not. Similarly, 1-nitro-pyrene (**23**) was formed, mainly in low oxidation potential DPFs, but 4-nitro-pyrene was not formed (Heeb et al., 2010). In other words, the nitration in particle filters was found to be regio-selective.

Figure 11 displays conversion efficiencies (CE) for nitro-PAHs of filter F1 on vehicle V1 (top) and filter F2 on vehicle V2 (bottom) in the cold- (blue) and hot- (red) WLTC. If concentrations after a filter exceeded those without filter, positive CEs are obtained, if nitro-PAHs are converted in the filter negative CEs are observed.

Figure 11: Conversion efficiencies of nitro-PAHs in filter F1 (top) and filter F2 (bottom) from cold- (blue) and hot-started (red) WLTCs. Conversion efficiencies (CEs) are calculated according to the formula $CE = ((\text{conc. with filter} / \text{conc. without filter}) - 1)$. Negative CEs indicate a reduction of nitro-PAHs, positive CEs indicate higher emissions after the filter. Respective CEs of seven individual nitro-PAHs together with sum values of all detected nitro-PAHs and sums of 2-ring-, 3-ring- and 4-ring-nitro-PAHs are displayed.

Conversion efficiencies (CE) for single nitro-PAHs and for nitro-PAH sums of filter F1 (top) vary considerably and no systematic trends could be observed. Such a stochastic behavior of the CE data for filter F1 was also observed for PAHs (Figure 7, top).

If we compare nitro-PAH (Fig. 11, bottom) and PAH (Fig. 7, bottom) trends for filter F2, we found a systematic behavior for PAHs, which were retained and converted to some degree. Especially the 5-ring and 6-ring PAHs, including the carcinogenic ones were converted with efficiencies of 30 to 60% (-0.3 to -0.6). No net reduction was observed for nitro-PAHs in filter F2 and exhaust concentrations remained comparably high with and without filter.

4.3. Emissions of polychlorinated dibenzodioxins/furans (PCDD/Fs)

Polychlorinated dibenzodioxins/furans are two classes of compounds which include in total 210 congeners, 75 PCDDs and 135 PCDFs. They can form in small amounts whenever chlorine-containing material is combusted. It has been observed that the combustion of leaded gasolines containing 1,2-dichloro-ethane as scavenger resulted in increased PCDD/F emissions. We have reported that PCDD/Fs can form *de novo* too in certain catalyzed diesel particle filters. So far, DPFs with a *de novo* formation potential for PCDD/Fs were mainly based on fuel-borne catalysts (FBCs). The use of copper-, copper/iron- and iron/potassium-based FBCs induced an immediate and intense secondary formation of PCDD/Fs in particle filters (Heeb et al. 2005, 2007, 2013). These filters did not pass the VERT-secondary emissions test. Hence they were not included in the VERT filter list and not approved for applications on construction machinery in Switzerland.

Figure 12 displays the chemical structures (**25-31**) of the seven toxic, 2,3,7,8-substituted dibenzodioxins. Among them 2,3,7,8-tetrachloro-dibenzodioxin (**25**) is the most toxic congener. Its toxic properties to humans and to animals have been studied in detail after the accidental release from a chemical plant in Seveso, Italy. 2,3,7,8-tetrachloro-dibenzodioxin (**25**) has also been used for the attempted murder of former Ukrainian president Victor Yushchenko on Sept. 2004 and its health impact on Victor Yushchenko has been reported (Sorg et al., 2009).

Figure 12: Chemical structures of the seven toxic PCDDs. Compounds **25** to **31** all include chlorine substitutions at positions 2,3,7 and 8, which are important to bind to the human aryl hydrocarbon receptor (AHR). Toxicity-equivalence factors (TEFs) in relation to the most toxic 2,3,7,8-tetrachloro-dibenzodioxin (**25**) are indicated.

Figure 13 displays the chemical structures (**32-41**) of the ten toxic 2,3,7,8-substituted dibenzofurans. Among them 2,3,4,7,8-tetrachloro-dibenzofuran (**34**) is the most toxic congener. Because all 2,3,7,8-substituted dibenzodioxins and furans bind to the human aryl hydrocarbon receptor, their relative toxicity has been determined and put in relation to the most toxic congener 2,3,7,8-TCDD (**25**), the so-called Seveso dioxin. Respective toxicity-equivalence factors (TEFs) vary three orders of magnitude from 0.001x for octachloro-dibenzodioxin (**31**) and octachloro-dibenzofuran (**41**) to 1.0 for 2,3,7,8-TCDD (**25**).

Figure 13: Chemical structures of the ten toxic PCDFs. Compounds **32** to **41** all include chlorine substitutions at positions 2,3,7 and 8, which are important to bind to the human aryl hydrocarbon receptor. Toxicity-equivalence factors (TEFs) in relation to the most toxic 2,3,7,8-tetrachloro-dibenzodioxin (**25**) are indicated.

PCDD/Fs are more than PAHs trace compounds in exhausts and levels of different congeners in dilute exhausts remain below 10 pg/m³ in most cases. The Swiss and German emission limit for municipal waste incinerators are set to 100 pg/m³.

It is interesting to notice that 2,3,7,8-substituted DD/Fs are the best ligands known that can bind strongly to the aryl hydrocarbon receptor. But PAHs, also named aryl hydrocarbons, are most abundant ligands present in combustion exhausts. The toxicity-equivalence factors of genotoxic PAHs like benzo(a)pyrene (**13**) are lower than those of PCDD/Fs. However, their contribution to the AHR-activity can be higher due to the higher PAH abundance as has been demonstrated (Wenger et al., 2008).

Figure 14 displays concentrations (pg/m^3) of the sums of all PCDD/Fs, all PCDDs and all PCDFs together with the toxicity-weighted 2,3,7,8-chlorinated dibenzodioxins/furans in dilute exhausts of vehicles V1 and V2 without and with filters F1 and F2. PCDD/F emissions in transient cycles exceeded those from steady-state driving in most cases as observed before for PAHs and nitro-PAHs.

Figure 14: Concentrations (pg/m^3) of PCDD/Fs in dilute vehicle exhausts from the cold- (blue) and hot-started (red) WLTC and the steady state cycle (black). Levels in CVS dilution air (gray) are given as well. Vehicles V1 and V2 without and with particle filters F1 and F2 are compared. Sums of all PCDD/Fs (left), PCDDs and PCDFs are displayed together with the toxic potential obtained from the toxicity-weighted sum of all 2,3,7,8-substituted DD/Fs (right).

Emissions under cold- (blue) and hot-start (red) conditions often are comparably high and range from 100-370, 60-180 and 10-90 pg/m^3 for the sums of PCDD/Fs, PCDDs and PCDFs, respectively, with one exception. PCDF emissions in the cold-started WLTC of V1 after filter F1 were about 5-times higher than in all other vehicle and filter configurations. Concentrations in dilution air from the CVS tunnel were as low as those from the steady-state cycle.

Figure 15 displays concentrations (pg/m^3) of the seven toxic PCDDs in dilute exhausts of vehicles V1 and V2 without and with filters F1 and F2. Emissions of the toxic PCDDs in transient cycles exceeded those from steady-state driving in most cases. The latter are as low as those of the CVS dilution air.

Concentrations of the toxic tetra-, penta- and hexa-chloro-DDs vary from 2 to 6 pg/m^3 and increase to 10 to 40 pg/m^3 for hepta- and octa-chloro-DDs. In most cases PCDD emissions in the cold- and hot-WLTC are comparable, especially for Cl_4 - to Cl_6 -congeners, with more variations for Cl_7 - and Cl_8 -DDs.

Figure 15: Concentrations (pg/m^3) of the seven toxic PCDDs in dilute vehicle exhausts from the cold- (blue) and hot-started (red) WLTC and the steady state cycle (black). Levels in CVS dilution air (gray) are given as well. Vehicles V1 and V2 without and with particle filters F1 and F2 are compared.

Figure 16 displays concentrations (pg/m^3) of the ten toxic PCDFs in dilute exhausts of vehicles V1 and V2 without and with filters F1 and F2. Once more, emissions of the toxic PCDFs in transient cycles exceeded those from steady-state driving. The latter are as low as those of the CVS dilution air (gray).

Concentrations of the toxic tetra-DFs are highest varying from 10 to 50 pg/m^3 . Those of the toxic penta-, hexa-, hepta- and octa-chloro-DFs were lower and varied from 1 to 10 pg/m^3 . In general, emissions in the cold- and hot-WLTC were often comparably high with the exception mentioned above where PCDF emissions in the cold-started WLTC of V1 after filter F1 were about 2 to 5-times higher than in all other vehicle and filter configurations.

Figure 16: Concentrations (pg/m^3) of the ten toxic PCDFs in dilute vehicle exhausts from the cold- (blue) and hot-started (red) WLTC and the steady state cycle (black). Levels in CVS dilution air (gray) are given as well. Vehicles V1 and V2 without and with particle filters F1 and F2 are compared.

It has to be mentioned that concentrations of toxic PCDDs and PCDFs are close to the levels of dilution air sampled from the CVS-tunnel. Thus we expect some experimental uncertainties which will add up when calculating conversion efficiencies of filters.

Figure 17: Conversion efficiencies of PCDDs and PCDFs in filter F1 (top) and filter F2 (bottom) from cold- (blue) and hot-started (red) WLTCs. Conversion efficiencies (CEs) are calculated according to the formula $CE = ((\text{conc. with filter} / \text{conc. without filter}) - 1)$. Negative CEs indicate a reduction of pollutants, positive CEs indicate higher emissions after the filter. Respective CEs are shown for the 7 toxic PCDDs, the 10 toxic PCDFs, the toxic potential weighted with respective toxicity equivalence factors, the sums all Cl₄-to Cl₈-PCDDs, PCDFs and PCDD/Fs.

Conversion efficiencies (CE) for single 2,3,7,8-substituted DD and DF of filter F1 (top) vary considerably. Under hot conditions (red) negative and under cold conditions (blue) positive CEs prevail (**Figure 17**, top). This stochastic behavior is also observed when the sums of PCDDs, PCDFs, PCDD/Fs and the toxic potential are considered.

If we compare data from filter F2, (**Fig. 17**, bottom), we found substantial variations of conversion efficiencies as well. However, conversion efficiencies for lower chlorinated congeners (Cl_4 , Cl_5) and the sums of all PCDDs, PCDFs and PCDD/Fs as well as the toxic potential are negative, indicating a net reduction in the filter. Efficiencies of 10% to 60% (-0.1 to -0.6) were obtained for these sums.

This compares with effects of filter F2 on PAHs, especially on 5-ring and 6-ring PAHs, which include the carcinogenic ones, with efficiencies of 30% to 60% (-0.3 to -0.6).

5. Impact of next-generation GPFs on the genotoxic potential of exhausts

Particle filters are widely used in various diesel vehicles today. They have been implemented in series already in the year 2000 in Euro-3 passenger cars (Peugeot 607, 98 kW, 2.2 L). With the implementation of a particle number emission limit of 6×10^{11} particles/km in 2009, all Euro-5 and post-Euro-5 diesel vehicles are now equipped with filter technology. This PN emission limit was also implemented for light-duty diesel vehicles. Since 2013, Euro-VI heavy-duty diesel vehicles also have to comply with a PN limit of 6×10^{11} particles/kWh and are equipped with particle filters too.

In parallel, construction machinery, buses for public transportation and many off-road diesel applications have been equipped with particle filter technology. The Swiss clean air act (Luftreinhalte-Verordnung, LRV) limited particle number emissions of construction machinery to 6×10^{11} particles/kWh already in 2009. Furthermore, it defines criteria to be met for filter technology for these applications. It is prescribed that particle number filtration efficiencies should be >98% for all particles in a size range of 23 and 400 nm. The application of such particle filters should not lead to an increase of toxic secondary pollutants and these conditions must be met after 2000 hours of field operation as well.

In other words, particle filters have been widely used for nearly two decades now in many diesel applications but are so far rarely applied for gasoline vehicles. With the support of our industrial partners could we test new particle filter technology specifically developed for gasoline vehicles.

Two GPFs, both without catalytic coating, were imbedded in the tailpipe system of two Euro-6b vehicles, which had to comply with a PN limit of 6×10^{12} particles/km. Vehicle V1, a Fiat 500X (1.6L, model year 2016) was equipped with MPI technology while vehicle V2, a VW Golf TSI (1.4 L, model year 2016), used a DI technology. Both vehicles could be retrofitted with well-integrated filters F1 and F2.

Figure 18 displays toxicity-weighted genotoxic potentials (ng benzo(a)pyrene equivalents/ m^3) of diluted exhausts of the MPI-vehicle V1 (Fiat 500X) and the GDI-vehicle V2 (VW Golf TSI). Both vehicles were tested without and with particle filters in the cold and hot-started WLTC.

Figure 18: Genotoxic potential (ng benzo(a)pyrene equivalents/m³) of PAH emissions of vehicles V1 and V2 in diluted exhausts of the cold- and hot-started WLTC. Both vehicles were tested without and with well-integrated particle filters. The eight genotoxic PAHs listed are represented according to the color code and their toxicity equivalence factors are given.

No positive effects of filter F1 on vehicle V1 on the genotoxic potential of diluted exhausts were detected. Levels and Pattern of different PAHs remained similar as well. However, filter F2 on vehicle V2 did lower the genotoxic potential of diluted exhausts by 30% and 60% in the cold- and hot-started WLTC, respectively. Comparing PAH patterns after filter F2 indicate that mainly higher-boiling 5-ring and 6-ring PAHs are retained and converted in the filter while for example the low-boiling 2-ring PAH naphthalene (blue) did penetrate the filter F2 and was released at similar concentrations.

6. Comparison of genotoxic potentials of GDI vehicles and proto-type filters

Within the GASOMEF project four proto-type particle filters for GDI vehicles have been tested under similar conditions at the chassis dynamometer of the FHB. However, the reference GDI-vehicle was different and a different fuel was used as well. An Euro-5 Volvo V60 (1.6 L) with higher PN emissions was used. The four proto-type filters tested included two filters without coating and two with catalytic coatings of unknown chemical nature.

Figure 19 displays the weighted genotoxic potential of undiluted exhausts of the Euro-5 GDI vehicle (Volvo V60, 1.6 L) in the cold- and hot-started WLTC. Benzo(a)pyrene (**13**, red) and dibenzo(ah)anthracene (**14**, pink), have the highest toxicity factor of 1.0, naphthalene (**1**, blue) has the lowest toxicity factor of 0.001.

Figure 19: Genotoxic potential (ng TEQ/m³) of PAH emissions of filtered and non-filtered GDI vehicle exhausts in the cold- and hot-started WLTC. The eight genotoxic PAHs are represented according to the given color code and their genotoxic potential with weighted toxicity equivalence factors. Concentrations in undiluted exhaust of the Euro-5 reference vehicle (Volvo, V60, 1.6 L) operated without filter and with four proto-type GPFs (GPF-1, -2, -3 and -4) are compared with data of the benchmark diesel vehicle (Peugeot 4008, 1.6 L, Euro-5) with DPF.

We concluded that the genotoxic potential of undiluted exhausts of the non-filtered Euro-5 GDI vehicle (Volvo V60, 1.6 L) is exceeding the one of the diesel vehicle with integrated filter 6- to 7-fold (**Figure 19**). The proto-type filters GPF-1, -2 and -3 lowered emissions of genotoxic PAHs by about 45%-70% in the cold and by 71%-83% in the hot WLTC, respectively.

GPF-4, which was not coated, had a moderate efficiency with respect to particle number emissions, and its impact on genotoxic emissions was small too. In the cold WLTC genotoxic PAH emissions were reduced by 10%, in the hot WLTC the even were 2-times higher after the filter than from the vehicle. In other words, this filter was not able to convert genotoxic PAHs, but presumably stored them to some degree, and released them again. Such store-and-release phenomena have been observed before for catalytically inactive DPFs.

7. Conclusions

We conclude that all GDI vehicles tested in this project and the GASOMEF project release relevant amounts of PAHs including genotoxic PAHs. However, PAH emissions of both Euro-6b vehicles (Fiat 500X and VW Golf FSI), which were tested in the AeroSolfd project, were lower than those of the Euro-5 reference vehicle (Volvo V60) in the GASOMEF project.

Genotoxic PAH emissions of vehicle V1, the Fiat 500X (Euro-6b), which used the MPI technology were 30%-40% lower than those of vehicle V2, the VW Golf FSI (Euro-6b) equipped with GDI technology. Even more pronounced were particle number effects of the GDI-vehicle (VW Golf), which were 6.1×10^{11} and 6.2×10^{11} particles/km in the cold and hot WLTC, respectively, while PN emissions of the MPI-vehicle (Fiat 500X) were 5x and 15x lower at 1.0×10^{11} and 0.4×10^{11} particles/km in the cold and hot WLTC.

Three of the four tested proto-type filters in the GASOMEF project did lower genotoxic PAH emissions by 45%-83% (**Figure 19**) while one filter showed no net reduction of PAHs (Munoz et al., 2018a).

One of the two filters tested in the AeroSolfd project (**Figure 18**) did lower genotoxic PAH emissions of the GDI vehicle (VW Golf) by 40% and 70%, while those of filter F1 on the MPI vehicle (Fiat 500X) could not convert genotoxic PAHs and in one case released stored material again.

No significant formation of nitro-PAHs could be detected in both filters. This could be an indication that nitrating species are not abundant in gasoline exhaust compared to diesel exhaust. Furthermore, higher temperatures and shorter residence times, which are reached in GPFs, do not favor a nitration of PAHs.

The *de novo* formation potential for PCDDs and PCDFs is considered as low and no indications for an efficient PCDD/F formation could be found under the given experimental conditions. Nevertheless, it has to be mentioned that the filters were not tested in the worst case scenario with a forced intake of chlorine via e.g. a co-combustion of scavengers like 1,2-dichloro-ethane.

We conclude that GPFs have a large potential to reduce nanoparticle emissions and to a lower extent also genotoxic PAHs. High PN efficiencies of >98% were obtained with the newly-designed particle filter F2 on vehicle V2, the GDI-vehicle (VW Golf) and genotoxic PAH emissions were lowered by 40%-70% as well. Filtration efficiencies of filter F1 on vehicle V1, the MPI-vehicle (Fiat 500X) of >95% are still high, but no net conversion of genotoxic PAHs could be observed in this case.

In summary, a big step towards best-available filter technologies for gasoline vehicles has been made that guarantees an efficient removal of soot particles. It is not clear yet, if a better combustion of accumulated soot and adsorbed PAHs can be achieved with optimized catalytic coatings. Indications that these critical compounds do accumulate in filters to be released again under high load operations have been observed for one of the two filters tested in the AeroSolfd project and in one of the four proto-type particle filters in the GASOMEF project (Munoz et al., 2018a).

The retrofitting of GPFs to Euro-5 and Euro-6b gasoline vehicles has been demonstrated with positive effects on particle number emissions and to some extent on genotoxic PAHs. Due to the substantial health risks associated with the inhalation of non-filtered diesel exhausts, which include numerous nanoparticles and relevant amounts of genotoxic PAHs, filters should be implemented in all next-generation vehicles (Euro-7) and retrofitted in high polluters such as Euro-4, Euro-5 and Euro-6 GDI-vehicles on a global scale.

Nanoparticles can act as Trojan horses, transporting adsorbed semi-volatile compounds such as genotoxic PAHs, nitro-PAHs and PCDD/Fs into the human lung, possibly even penetrating the alveolar membrane. This is a serious health threat and well documented for miners that were exposed to non-filtered diesel exhausts (Silverman et al. 2012. Koutros et al., 2023).

We reported that gasoline vehicle exhausts also contain numerous soot-like nanoparticles carrying genotoxic PAHs. In this respect they have a similar chemical composition like the one of non-treated diesel exhausts. Non-treated diesel exhaust is considered as class 1 carcinogen by the WHO, inducing lung cancer in humans. We expect that the WHO will also classify non-filtered exhausts of gasoline vehicles, hopefully soon in the fast growing vehicle market.

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Appendix 1: PAH concentrations in diluted vehicle exhausts

Concentration in dilute exhaust: ^{a,b)}	BL-420 [ng/Nm ³]	BL-421 [ng/Nm ³]	V1F1T1C-422 [ng/Nm ³]	V1F1T1H-423 [ng/Nm ³]	V1F1S1H-424 [ng/Nm ³]
Genotoxic potential	0.8	2.6	3.8	3.2	0.8
Sum carcinogenic PAHs (EPA)	6.9	11.0	34.0	21.0	9.8
Sum carcinogenic PAHs (WHO, IARC)	7.2	11.0	38.0	21.0	9.9
Sum priority PAHs	830	1500	2700	1700	640
Naphthalene	230	1200	1200	480	180
Acenaphthylene	4	4	47	12	3
Acenaphthene	15	11	69	28	10
Fluorene	42	33	160	79	25
Phenanthrene	400	180	830	860	270
Anthracene	5	5	21	25	10
Fluoranthene	94	47	220	160	84
Pyrene	40	28	120	90	45
Benzo-a-anthracene	1.2	2.1	4.9	3.2	1.2
Chrysene	4.1	5.7	20.0	9.4	6.9
Benzo-b-fluoranthene	0.7	1.2	4.6	3.4	0.8
Benzo-k-fluoranthene	0.4	0.8	2.0	1.6	0.5
Benzo-a-pyrene	0.2	0.4	0.9	0.8	0.2
Indeno-123-cd-pyrene	0.2	0.4	1.3	1.5	0.2
Dibenzo-ah-anthracene	0.1	0.5	0.2	0.9	0.2
Benzo-ghi-perylene	0.4	0.1	4.0	0.2	0.1
Sample volume dry [Nm ³]	2.246	2.487	1.270	1.238	4.259

a) Only detectable PAHs were summed and included into the calculation of the corresponding emission factors.

b) PAH-Isomers that were not detectable at a signal/noise ratio of 3 are not reported in the table.

Appendix 1: PAH concentrations in diluted vehicle exhausts (continued)

Concentration in dilute exhaust: ^{a,b)}	BL-420 [ng/Nm ³]	BL-421 [ng/Nm ³]	V1T1C-425 [ng/Nm ³]	V1T1H-426 [ng/Nm ³]	V1S1H-427 [ng/Nm ³]
Genotoxic potential	0.8	2.6	2.8	3.0	0.7
Sum carcinogenic PAHs (EPA)	6.9	11.0	34.0	22.0	6.3
Sum carcinogenic PAHs (WHO, IARC)	7.2	11.0	34.0	22.0	6.5
Sum priority PAHs	830	1500	2300	2200	690
Naphthalene	230	1200	650	390	190
Acenaphthylene	4	4	10	7	3
Acenaphthene	15	11	35	37	12
Fluorene	42	33	90	99	33
Phenanthrene	400	180	960	1300	320
Anthracene	5	5	20	19	12
Fluoranthene	94	47	290	260	74
Pyrene	40	28	160	52	36
Benzo-a-anthracene	1.2	2.1	4.0	2.8	0.7
Chrysene	4.1	5.7	24.0	11.0	4.0
Benzo-b-fluoranthene	0.7	1.2	2.8	3.0	0.7
Benzo-k-fluoranthene	0.4	0.8	1.7	1.9	0.4
Benzo-a-pyrene	0.2	0.4	0.5	0.7	0.2
Indeno-123-cd-pyrene	0.2	0.4	0.7	1.5	0.1
Dibenzo-ah-anthracene	0.1	0.5	0.6	0.9	0.1
Benzo-ghi-perylene	0.4	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.2
Sample volume dry [Nm ³]	2.246	2.487	1.216	1.247	4.212

a) Only detectable PAHs were summed and included into the calculation of the corresponding emission factors.

b) PAH-isomers that were not detectable at a signal/noise ratio of 3 are not reported in the table.

Appendix 1: PAH concentrations in diluted vehicle exhausts (continued)

Concentration in dilute exhaust: ^{a,b)}	BL-420 [ng/Nm ³]	BL-421 [ng/Nm ³]	V2T1C-431 [ng/Nm ³]	V2F2T1H-429 [ng/Nm ³]	V2F2S1H-430 [ng/Nm ³]
Genotoxic potential	0.8	2.6	3.9	1.8	0.6
Sum carcinogenic PAHs (EPA)	6.9	11.0	10.0	12.0	2.9
Sum carcinogenic PAHs (WHO, IARC)	7.2	11.0	11.0	13.0	3.1
Sum priority PAHs	830	1500	2900	2500	810
Naphthalene	230	1200	1800	870	330
Acenaphthylene	4	4	110	120	37
Acenaphthene	15	11	37	27	9
Fluorene	42	33	110	140	47
Phenanthrene	400	180	650	990	270
Anthracene	5	5	30	36	16
Fluoranthene	94	47	110	170	62
Pyrene	40	28	66	87	40
Benzo-a-anthracene	1.2	2.1	1.3	1.7	0.5
Chrysene	4.1	5.7	4.8	7.4	1.7
Benzo-b-fluoranthene	0.7	1.2	1.1	1.3	0.3
Benzo-k-fluoranthene	0.4	0.8	1.0	0.8	0.1
Benzo-a-pyrene	0.2	0.4	0.4	0.3	0.1
Indeno-123-cd-pyrene	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.4	0.1
Dibenzo-ah-anthracene	0.1	0.5	1.2	0.1	0.0
Benzo-ghi-perylene	0.4	0.1	0.1	0.6	0.2
Sample volume dry [Nm ³]	2.246	2.487	1.255	1.205	4.349

a) Only detectable PAHs were summed and included into the calculation of the corresponding emission factors.

b) PAH-Isomers that were not detectable at a signal/noise ratio of 3 are not reported in the table.

Appendix 1: PAH concentrations in diluted vehicle exhausts (continued)

Concentration in dilute exhaust: ^{a,b)}	BL-420 [ng/Nm ³]	BL-421 [ng/Nm ³]	V2T1C-432 [ng/Nm ³]	V2T1H-433 [ng/Nm ³]	V2S1H-434 [ng/Nm ³]
Genotoxic potential	0.8	2.6	5.5	4.5	1.3
Sum carcinogenic PAHs (EPA)	6.9	11.0	19.0	22.0	6.5
Sum carcinogenic PAHs (WHO, IARC)	7.2	11.0	20.0	25.0	7.2
Sum priority PAHs	830	1500	2500	1500	570
Naphthalene	230	1200	1800	730	100
Acenaphthylene	4	4	60	29	1
Acenaphthene	15	11	14	15	9
Fluorene	42	33	53	50	30
Phenanthrene	400	180	380	440	310
Anthracene	5	5	30	30	7
Fluoranthene	94	47	88	120	69
Pyrene	40	28	49	60	31
Benzo-a-anthracene	1.2	2.1	1.7	2.0	0.8
Chrysene	4.1	5.7	9.3	12.0	3.1
Benzo-b-fluoranthene	0.7	1.2	1.7	2.0	0.6
Benzo-k-fluoranthene	0.4	0.8	1.4	1.3	0.3
Benzo-a-pyrene	0.2	0.4	1.6	1.1	0.3
Indeno-123-cd-pyrene	0.2	0.4	1.5	1.8	0.8
Dibenzo-ah-anthracene	0.1	0.5	1.4	1.8	0.6
Benzo-ghi-perylene	0.4	0.1	1.8	2.3	0.7
Sample volume dry [Nm ³]	2.246	2.487	1.203	1.117	3.771

a) Only detectable PAHs were summed and included into the calculation of the corresponding emission factors.

b) PAH-isomers that were not detectable at a signal/noise ratio of 3 are not reported in the table.

Appendix 2: Nitro-PAH concentrations in diluted vehicle exhausts

Concentration in dilute exhaust: ^{a,b)}	BL-420 [ng/Nm ³]	BL-421 [ng/Nm ³]	V1F1T1C-422 [ng/Nm ³]	V1F1T1H-423 [ng/Nm ³]	V1F1S1H-424 [ng/Nm ³]
Sum nitro-PAHs	0.93	1.00	2.60	5.10	2.20
Sum 2-ring nitro-PAHs	0.93	0.97	1.60	4.00	1.80
Sum 3-ring nitro-PAHs			0.75	0.66	0.33
Sum 4-ring nitro-PAHs		0.04	0.32	0.48	0.09
1-N-Naphthalene	0.80	0.83	1.20	3.30	1.60
2-N-Naphthalene	0.12	0.13	0.40	0.67	0.21
9-N-Anthracene			0.69	0.61	0.31
9-N-Phenanthrene			0.02	0.05	0.02
3-N-Phenanthrene			0.04		
3-N-Fluoranthene		0.03	0.04		0.02
1-N-Pyrene		0.01	0.28	0.48	0.07
Sample volume dry [Nm ³]	2.246	2.487	1.270	1.238	4.259

a) Only detectable nitro-PAHs were summed and included into the calculation of the corresponding emission factors.

b) Nitro-PAHs that were not detectable at a signal/noise ratio of 3 are not reported in the table.

Appendix 2: Nitro-PAH concentrations in diluted vehicle exhausts (continued)

Concentration in dilute exhaust: ^{a,b)}	BL-420 [ng/Nm ³]	BL-421 [ng/Nm ³]	V1T1C-425 [ng/Nm ³]	V1T1H-426 [ng/Nm ³]	V1S1H-427 [ng/Nm ³]
Sum nitro-PAHs	0.93	1.00	7.60	4.20	1.30
Sum 2-ring nitro-PAHs	0.93	0.97	5.30	2.60	1.00
Sum 3-ring nitro-PAHs			1.30	0.73	0.25
Sum 4-ring nitro-PAHs		0.04	1.10	0.88	0.06
1-N-Naphthalene	0.80	0.83	4.10	1.90	0.73
2-N-Naphthalene	0.12	0.13	1.20	0.71	0.30
9-N-Anthracene			1.20	0.67	0.23
9-N-Phenanthrene			0.08	0.06	0.02
3-N-Phenanthrene					
3-N-Fluoranthene		0.03	0.10	0.08	0.01
1-N-Pyrene		0.01	0.98	0.80	0.05
Sample volume dry [Nm ³]	2.246	2.487	1.216	1.247	4.212

a) Only detectable nitro-PAHs were summed and included into the calculation of the corresponding emission factors.

b) Nitro-PAHs that were not detectable at a signal/noise ratio of 3 are not reported in the table.

Appendix 2: Nitro-PAH concentrations in diluted vehicle exhausts (continued)

Concentration in dilute exhaust: ^{a,b)}	BL-420 [ng/Nm ³]	BL-421 [ng/Nm ³]	V2F2T1C-431 [ng/Nm ³]	V2F2T1H-429 [ng/Nm ³]	V2F2S1H-430 [ng/Nm ³]
Sum nitro-PAHs	0.93	1.00	4.30	4.10	1.30
Sum 2-ring nitro-PAHs	0.93	0.97	3.70	2.80	1.10
Sum 3-ring nitro-PAHs			0.62	1.10	0.17
Sum 4-ring nitro-PAHs		0.04		0.16	0.02
1-N-Naphthalene	0.80	0.83	3.00	2.40	0.85
2-N-Naphthalene	0.12	0.13	0.73	0.47	0.25
9-N-Anthracene			0.54	0.52	0.15
9-N-Phenanthrene			0.08	0.62	0.02
3-N-Phenanthrene					
3-N-Fluoranthene		0.03		0.13	0.01
1-N-Pyrene		0.01		0.03	0.01
Sample volume dry [Nm ³]	2.246	2.487	1.255	1.205	4.349

a) Only detectable nitro-PAHs were summed and included into the calculation of the corresponding emission factors.

b) Nitro-PAHs that were not detectable at a signal/noise ratio of 3 are not reported in the table.

Appendix 2: Nitro-PAH concentrations in diluted vehicle exhausts (continued)

Concentration in dilute exhaust: ^{a,b)}	BL-420 [ng/Nm ³]	BL-421 [ng/Nm ³]	V2T1C-432 [ng/Nm ³]	V2T1H-433 [ng/Nm ³]	V2S1H-434 [ng/Nm ³]
Sum nitro-PAHs	0.93	1.00	3.10	3.50	1.80
Sum 2-ring nitro-PAHs	0.93	0.97	2.40	2.50	1.70
Sum 3-ring nitro-PAHs			0.67	0.96	0.09
Sum 4-ring nitro-PAHs		0.04			0.05
1-N-Naphthalene	0.80	0.83	1.90	1.90	1.50
2-N-Naphthalene	0.12	0.13	0.55	0.60	0.23
9-N-Anthracene			0.59	0.83	0.07
9-N-Phenanthrene			0.09	0.13	0.02
3-N-Phenanthrene					
3-N-Fluoranthene		0.03			0.01
1-N-Pyrene		0.01			0.03
Sample volume dry [Nm ³]	2.246	2.487	1.203	1.117	3.771

a) Only detectable nitro-PAHs were summed and included into the calculation of the corresponding emission factors.

b) Nitro-PAHs that were not detectable at a signal/noise ratio of 3 are not reported in the table.

Appendix 3: PCDD/F concentrations in diluted vehicle exhausts

Concentration in dilute exhaust: a,b)	BL-420 [pg/Nm ³]	BL-421 [pg/Nm ³]	V1F1T1C-422 [pg/Nm ³]	V1F1T1H-423 [pg/Nm ³]	V1F1S1H-424 [pg/Nm ³]
I-TEQ sum	4.3	1.9	15.0	3.5	2.3
Tetrachlorodibenzodioxins	3	12	23	13	7
Pentachlorodibenzodioxins	2	13	13	11	6
Hexachlorodibenzodioxins	3	7	21	8	4
Heptachlorodibenzodioxins	8	7	44	12	5
Octachlorodibenzodioxin	8	9	31	17	6
Sum PCDD	23	48	130	62	29
Tetrachlorodibenzofurans	37	6	140	23	21
Pentachlorodibenzofurans	3	2	29	400	2
Hexachlorodibenzofurans	3	0	33	0	0
Heptachlorodibenzofurans	5	3	36	6	2
Octachlorodibenzofuran	1	1	11	2	0
Sum PCDF	48	11	250	430	25
2,3,7,8-Tetrachlorodibenzodioxin	0.9	0.3	2.6	0.5	0.5
1,2,3,7,8-Pentachlorodibenzodioxin	0.5	0.4	1.6	0.5	0.2
1,2,3,4,7,8-Hexachlorodibenzodioxin	0.3	0.5	1.0	0.8	0.2
1,2,3,6,7,8-Hexachlorodibenzodioxin	1.1	1.7	5.4	1.6	1.2
1,2,3,7,8,9-Hexachlorodibenzodioxin	0.9	0.3	0.8	1.1	0.5
1,2,3,4,6,7,8-Heptachlorodibenzodioxin	3.7	4.4	25.0	8.3	3.5
Octachlorodibenzodioxin	8.3	9.3	31.0	17.0	6.2
2,3,7,8-Tetrachlorodibenzofuran	18.0	2.8	57.0	10.0	10.0
1,2,3,7,8-Pentachlorodibenzofuran	1.0	0.3	3.6	0.7	0.2
2,3,4,7,8-Pentachlorodibenzofuran	1.4	1.0	5.3	1.6	0.6
1,2,3,4,7,8-Hexachlorodibenzofuran	1.0	0.5	5.3	0.9	0.2
1,2,3,6,7,8-Hexachlorodibenzofuran	0.6	0.5	4.4	0.9	0.3
1,2,3,7,8,9-Hexachlorodibenzofuran	0.5	0.6	1.2	1.0	0.3
2,3,4,6,7,8-Hexachlorodibenzofuran	1.0	0.4	6.6	1.2	0.2
1,2,3,4,6,7,8-Heptachlorodibenzofuran	2.9	1.9	21.0	3.0	1.3
1,2,3,4,7,8,9-Heptachlorodibenzofuran	0.7	0.7	4.2	0.6	
Octachlorodibenzofuran	1.1	0.8	11.0	1.8	0.5
Recovery (Sampling)	0.77	0.69	0.46	0.59	0.55
Sample volume dilute exhaust [Nm ³]	2.25	2.49	1.27	1.24	4.26

a) Only detectable PCDD/F isomers were summed and included into the calculation of the corresponding emission factors.

b) PCDD/F-isomers that were not detectable at a signal/noise ratio of 3 are not reported in the table.

Appendix 3: PCDD/F concentrations in diluted vehicle exhausts (continued)

E-Factors of samples: a,b)	BL-420 [pg/Nm ³]	BL-421 [pg/Nm ³]	V1T1C-425 [pg/Nm ³]	V1T1H-426 [pg/Nm ³]	V1S1H-427 [pg/Nm ³]
I-TEQ sum	4.3	1.9	6.0	7.4	1.4
Tetrachlorodibenzodioxins	3	12	38	35	10
Pentachlorodibenzodioxins	2	13	50	24	11
Hexachlorodibenzodioxins	3	7	25	20	4
Heptachlorodibenzodioxins	8	7	22	13	3
Octachlorodibenzodioxin	8	9	18	35	4
Sum PCDD	23	48	150	130	32
Tetrachlorodibenzofurans	37	6	64	4	14
Pentachlorodibenzofurans	3	2	4	2	1
Hexachlorodibenzofurans	3	0	0	0	0
Heptachlorodibenzofurans	5	3	5	2	3
Octachlorodibenzofuran	1	1	1	2	0
Sum PCDF	48	11	74	9	18
2,3,7,8-Tetrachlorodibenzodioxin	0.9	0.3	1.3	1.5	0.2
1,2,3,7,8-Pentachlorodibenzodioxin	0.5	0.4	0.9	1.2	0.2
1,2,3,4,7,8-Hexachlorodibenzodioxin	0.3	0.5		1.2	0.2
1,2,3,6,7,8-Hexachlorodibenzodioxin	1.1	1.7	5.8	6.0	1.0
1,2,3,7,8,9-Hexachlorodibenzodioxin	0.9	0.3	2.9	3.7	0.4
1,2,3,4,6,7,8-Heptachlorodibenzodioxin	3.7	4.4	11.0	12.0	1.7
Octachlorodibenzodioxin	8.3	9.3	18.0	35.0	4.1
2,3,7,8-Tetrachlorodibenzofuran	18.0	2.8	23.0	23.0	5.8
1,2,3,7,8-Pentachlorodibenzofuran	1.0	0.3	0.9	1.1	0.2
2,3,4,7,8-Pentachlorodibenzofuran	1.4	1.0	1.6	2.1	0.5
1,2,3,4,7,8-Hexachlorodibenzofuran	1.0	0.5		1.8	0.2
1,2,3,6,7,8-Hexachlorodibenzofuran	0.6	0.5		2.4	0.3
1,2,3,7,8,9-Hexachlorodibenzofuran	0.5	0.6		1.7	0.3
2,3,4,6,7,8-Hexachlorodibenzofuran	1.0	0.4	0.8	1.2	0.2
1,2,3,4,6,7,8-Heptachlorodibenzofuran	2.9	1.9	2.3	2.9	0.9
1,2,3,4,7,8,9-Heptachlorodibenzofuran	0.7	0.7		1.9	0.3
Octachlorodibenzofuran	1.1	0.8	1.1	1.5	0.3
Recovery (Sampling)	0.77	0.69	0.33	0.55	0.54
Sample volume dilute exhaust [Nm ³]	2.25	2.49	1.22	1.25	4.21

a) Only detectable PCDD/F isomers were summed and included into the calculation of the corresponding emission factors.

b) PCDD/F-Isomers that were not detectable at a signal/noise ratio of 3 are not reported in the table.

Appendix 3: PCDD/F concentrations in diluted vehicle exhausts (continued)

Concentration in dilute exhaust: a,b)	BL-420 [pg/Nm ³]	BL-421 [pg/Nm ³]	V2F2T1C-431 [pg/Nm ³]	V2F2T1H-429 [pg/Nm ³]	V2F2S1H-430 [pg/Nm ³]
I-TEQ sum	4.3	1.9	3.9	5.5	1.4
Tetrachlorodibenzodioxins	3	12	35	32	6
Pentachlorodibenzodioxins	2	13	24	4	8
Hexachlorodibenzodioxins	3	7	19	18	3
Heptachlorodibenzodioxins	8	7	13	13	17
Octachlorodibenzodioxin	8	9	13	19	3
Sum PCDD	23	48	100	87	37
Tetrachlorodibenzofurans	37	6	35	73	14
Pentachlorodibenzofurans	3	2	2	3	1
Hexachlorodibenzofurans	3	0	0	0	0
Heptachlorodibenzofurans	5	3	2	4	1
Octachlorodibenzofuran	1	1	2	2	0
Sum PCDF	48	11	41	82	16
2,3,7,8-Tetrachlorodibenzodioxin	0.9	0.3	0.5	0.7	0.2
1,2,3,7,8-Pentachlorodibenzodioxin	0.5	0.4	0.4	0.5	0.3
1,2,3,4,7,8-Hexachlorodibenzodioxin	0.3	0.5	0.7	0.8	0.3
1,2,3,6,7,8-Hexachlorodibenzodioxin	1.1	1.7	4.6	5.3	1.0
1,2,3,7,8,9-Hexachlorodibenzodioxin	0.9	0.3	2.7	2.4	0.5
1,2,3,4,6,7,8-Heptachlorodibenzodioxin	3.7	4.4	8.9	11.0	1.1
Octachlorodibenzodioxin	8.3	9.3	13.0	19.0	3.1
2,3,7,8-Tetrachlorodibenzofuran	18.0	2.8	13.0	24.0	4.0
1,2,3,7,8-Pentachlorodibenzofuran	1.0	0.3	0.7	0.7	0.4
2,3,4,7,8-Pentachlorodibenzofuran	1.4	1.0	1.2	1.4	0.4
1,2,3,4,7,8-Hexachlorodibenzofuran	1.0	0.5	0.9	1.0	0.5
1,2,3,6,7,8-Hexachlorodibenzofuran	0.6	0.5	0.7	1.0	0.4
1,2,3,7,8,9-Hexachlorodibenzofuran	0.5	0.6	0.8	0.9	0.4
2,3,4,6,7,8-Hexachlorodibenzofuran	1.0	0.4	0.7	1.2	0.3
1,2,3,4,6,7,8-Heptachlorodibenzofuran	2.9	1.9	4.1	3.2	0.9
1,2,3,4,7,8,9-Heptachlorodibenzofuran	0.7	0.7	0.8	1.0	0.4
Octachlorodibenzofuran	1.1	0.8	1.9	1.5	0.4
Recovery (Sampling)	0.77	0.69	0.49	1.47	0.73
Sample volume dilute exhaust [Nm ³]	2.25	2.49	1.26	1.21	4.35

a) Only detectable PCDD/F isomers were summed and included into the calculation of the corresponding emission factors.

b) PCDD/F-Isomers that were not detectable at a signal/noise ratio of 3 are not reported in the table.

Appendix 3: PCDD/F concentrations in diluted vehicle exhausts (continued)

Concentration in dilute exhaust: a,b)	BL-420 [pg/Nm ³]	BL-421 [pg/Nm ³]	V2T1C-432 [pg/Nm ³]	V2T1H-433 [pg/Nm ³]	V2S1H-434 [pg/Nm ³]
I-TEQ sum	4.3	1.9	5.4	7.8	1.4
Tetrachlorodibenzodioxins	3	12	43	33	10
Pentachlorodibenzodioxins	2	13	47	44	10
Hexachlorodibenzodioxins	3	7	19	25	4
Heptachlorodibenzodioxins	8	7	13	51	5
Octachlorodibenzodioxin	8	9	13	40	6
Sum PCDD	23	48	140	190	35
Tetrachlorodibenzofurans	37	6	36	61	22
Pentachlorodibenzofurans	3	2	5	8	1
Hexachlorodibenzofurans	3	0	0	0	0
Heptachlorodibenzofurans	5	3	4	12	2
Octachlorodibenzofuran	1	1	1	8	0
Sum PCDF	48	11	46	90	24
2,3,7,8-Tetrachlorodibenzodioxin	0.9	0.3	1.6	1.7	0.2
1,2,3,7,8-Pentachlorodibenzodioxin	0.5	0.4	0.5	0.5	0.1
1,2,3,4,7,8-Hexachlorodibenzodioxin	0.3	0.5	0.5	0.7	0.2
1,2,3,6,7,8-Hexachlorodibenzodioxin	1.1	1.7	4.3	5.5	1.3
1,2,3,7,8,9-Hexachlorodibenzodioxin	0.9	0.3	3.0	3.4	0.5
1,2,3,4,6,7,8-Heptachlorodibenzodioxin	3.7	4.4	8.5	34.0	3.3
Octachlorodibenzodioxin	8.3	9.3	13.0	40.0	5.8
2,3,7,8-Tetrachlorodibenzofuran	18.0	2.8	17.0	31.0	6.6
1,2,3,7,8-Pentachlorodibenzofuran	1.0	0.3	0.7	1.0	0.3
2,3,4,7,8-Pentachlorodibenzofuran	1.4	1.0	1.3	1.9	0.3
1,2,3,4,7,8-Hexachlorodibenzofuran	1.0	0.5	0.8	0.7	0.2
1,2,3,6,7,8-Hexachlorodibenzofuran	0.6	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.2
1,2,3,7,8,9-Hexachlorodibenzofuran	0.5	0.6	0.6	0.9	0.2
2,3,4,6,7,8-Hexachlorodibenzofuran	1.0	0.4	0.5	0.9	0.2
1,2,3,4,6,7,8-Heptachlorodibenzofuran	2.9	1.9	2.3	6.0	0.9
1,2,3,4,7,8,9-Heptachlorodibenzofuran	0.7	0.7	0.4	1.0	0.2
Octachlorodibenzofuran	1.1	0.8	1.3	8.1	0.5
Recovery (Sampling)	0.77	0.69	0.44	0.63	0.58
Sample volume dilute exhaust [Nm ³]	2.25	2.49	1.20	1.12	3.77

a) Only detectable PCDD/F isomers were summed and included into the calculation of the corresponding emission factors.

b) PCDD/F-isomers that were not detectable at a signal/noise ratio of 3 are not reported in the table.